

CONTEXTUAL MEANS OF EXPRESSING PHASE IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES

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Abstract

Therefore, due to the absence of a designated category in the grammatical structure of English and in the sense in which it presented in Uzbek, the role of phase indicators in a sentence can perform temporal adverbs, circumstantial indicators, separate lexical units of different parts of speech and combinations of words, which, with the help of context, express the relation of a phenomenon to a specific time span.

Keywords: *Contextual means, indicators, phase, phenomenon, temporary adverbs, unions, initials.*

So, as we have already noted earlier, the main phase indicator in Uzbek is the grammatical category of aspect, which helps a native speaker to easily determine one or another phase phenomenon or process. There are ambiguous points of view on the issue the existence of this category in the English language. However, we are still we are inclined to the opinion of linguist, who believes that the categories of the species as such does not exist in English. The researcher claims that aspectual meanings and tenses in English are closely interconnected with each other, i.e. view in English is represented through tense verb forms, and, accordingly, time and aspect in this language constitute a

single species-temporal system of the language [5,208].

In English, temporal adverbs, circumstantial indicators, individual lexical units of different parts of speech and combinations words that, with the help of context, express the relation of the phenomenon to specific time period. Examples of these lexical units may be the following: *once upon a time, firstly, then, at first, later, endlessly, in the end, after all, day by day, at that time, earlier*, and many more.

For example, to indicate in a sentence the phase of the beginning is widely circumstantial indicators of phase are used, such as:

a) indicators to indicate the phenomenon or process that will begin soon. So, the phase of the onset of action can be expressed indirectly through words that do not contain the meaning of initiation, however implicitly reflecting the idea of the beginning in combination with the verb and a prepositional combination that has an adverbial function, for example *after a while: then, suddenly, when*, (*After a while he suddenly began to sing - After a while, he suddenly began to sing.*) Other examples of this groups can serve the following indicators: *on the verge of, on the brink of, on the edge of, to be about to do smth* (*Being on the verge of breakdown, he left the room - Asabi buzilgan sharoitda u xonani tark etdi*) [3,81];

b) indicators to indicate the emergence or formation process/phenomenon. In this case, it should be said that the use of or another indicator depends on the nature or speed of occurrence phenomenon or process, because in some cases the onset phase requires a certain level of training or the cost of a certain amount time (for example: *little by little the apple began to turn black; immediately began rain*). In English, circumstantial indicators of occurrence and becoming of action are indicated by the following words and combinations words: *instantly, immediately, suddenly, gradually, by degrees, piece by piece, little by little, all of a sudden, inch by inch, methodically, in less than no time, at once, bit by bit*,

straight away, then and there , et (*I felt really tired of all a sudden - To'satdan men juda charchaganimni his qildim*)[4,89];

c) indicators to indicate the starting point of a phenomenon or process. In this case, we are dealing with circumstantial indicators, which determine the starting point of the indicated phenomenon and further its development: *from the (very) beginning (of), from this hour/ day/ month/ year on, from the start, from now on, from the outset (From this day on you show me your diary - Shu kundan boshlab siz menga kundaligingizni ko'rsatasiz)*;

d) an indicator to indicate the beginning of a phenomenon or process directly. To units conveying a general meaning initiatives can be attributed: *in the beginning / start, initially, primarily (Primarily they were angry - Dastlab ular g'azablanishdi)*.

To mark the continuation phase in English also there are certain circumstantial indicators, namely:

a) indicators to indicate the duration of action. In this subtype, the duration of the phenomenon can be represented as extra long or ultra short, and also be limited to a specific time period.

However, in emphatic sentences, the indicated temporary limitation can be figurative (*I hadn't seen her for ages - Men uni bir necha yillar davomida ko'rmagan edim*). Examples of this subgroup are: *for a (long) while, for a long ... minutes, for ... seconds/ minutes/ hours/ years, an instant, a moment, a second, for several seconds/ hours/ years (He stared at me for a while and then passed through – He stared at me for a while and then moved on - U bir muddat menga tikilib qoldi va keyin davom etdi)* [3,105];

b) indicators to indicate the presence of pauses in the process of the phenomenon. Phase continuation in terms of the presence or absence of pauses is characterized concepts such as "discontinuity" and "continuity", therefore specific lexical units allow us to divide the situation into several stages: *for one*

hour a day/ week/ month, once/ twice a week, between moments of ..., every day/ month/ year, in the space of several days, around the clock, per hour, continuously, perpetually, non-stop, with a break, on and on, day after day, all the year round , et (Lisa visited the doctor in the space of several months - Liza bir necha oy oraliq'ida shifokorga tashrif buyurdi);

c) indicators to indicate the infinity of the course of action. This subgroup is necessary for marking situations that do not have internal limit. Here we can include the following indicators: *(time) without end, interminably, endlessly, incessantly, unendingly, for the rest of eternity, till the crack of doom, forever, for the entire life (I will be part of you **forever** - Men abadiy sizning bir qisminingiz bo'lib qolaman) [3,123];*

d) indicators to indicate the limit of the situation. Next the subgroup aims to set the initial and final limits actions/situations: *from start to finish, from beginning till end, from day to night et (You should study hard **from start to finish** if you want to get a good job - Agar kelgusida yaxshi yashashni istasangiz, boshidan oxirigacha qattiq o'qishingiz kerak)*

e) indicators to indicate a situation with a change in intensity. This subgroup determines, first of all, emotionally colored sentences, thereby drawing attention to the increase or decreasing the intensity of the situation: *with years, more and more, bigger and bigger, increasingly, with every minute/ hour/ day/ year, fatter and fatter, et (The night grew darker and darker, so Tom barely saw a thing in his face - Tun qorong'ilashib borardi, shuning uchun Tom uning yuzida bir narsani zo'rg'a ko'rdi).*

To express the completion phase of an action or process in English, the following subgroups of indicators are used:

a) indicators indicating the approach of the action to the end. The specificity of these lexical units is that they are not indicate the final point of action, but only describe the final part of the period of time that is occupied by a

particular action: *to the end, at the end, in the end, in the conclusion, in the final, at the expiration of* (In the conclusion the son visited his mother - *Natijada bola hali ham onasini yoniga tashrif buyurdi*);

b) indicators that serve to convey the end of the action subjective assessment. The following lexical units are required for obtaining additional emotional coloring of the proposal. FROM with the help of this subgroup of indicators, the connotation of something is conveyed long-awaited, and the proposal itself can be negative shade: *after all, at long last, ultimately, in the long run, eventually, at last, in the end of all* (Thank you very much Steve. In the long run you've remembered the date of my birthday –*Katta rahmat Stiv. Nima bo'lganida ham siz mening tug'ilgan kunimni esladigiz!*);

c) indicators indicating suddenness or gradualness completion of an action or process. The specificity of this subgroup is that it uses indicators that also indicate the emergence and formation of the action (the phase of the beginning), therefore, to determine phase is possible only with the help of context. Surprise indicators: *right away, immediately, abruptly, on the spot, in less than no time, instantly, suddenly, straight away, all of a sudden, at once, then and there, in a moment, at a moment's notice, in a trice/ moment* (The room was emptied all of a sudden - *Xona to'satdan bo'shatildi*) [4,45]; *fade-out indicators: drop by drop, bit by bit, step by step, by degrees, gradually, little by little, methodically, piece by piece , et* (Gradually the rain ceased - *Asta-sekin yomg'ir to'xtadi*) [4,78].

A separate group can designate a group of adverbs of time, which, in combination with a verb in a specific tense form designate one of three phases of the course of action:

- temporary adverbs of the initial phase, which began at the time of speech or will start soon: *yet, next week, tomorrow, next decade, soon*;

- temporary adverbs of the continue phase: *always, often, usually, sometimes, never, today, now, at the moment, rarely, seldom, still*;

- temporary adverbs of the final phase: *before, lately, recently, once, already, yesterday, last month/week/year.*

Adverbs of the first subgroup define situations that began before moment of speech, or begin in the near (sometimes indefinite) time. Interesting is the fact that the initial phase can be expressed with using the past tense form, which is usually used to indication of the completed action. In this case, it appears an action that began in the past and continues at the present moment of speech: *He left for the shop yet - U endigina do'kongga ketdi.* In other words, you can express this sentence in the following way: He began to move in side of the store. That is, a certain person began an action, but it has not yet been finished (the person has not yet come to the store).

Adverbs of the second subgroup characterize recurring situations or those that flow at the moment of speech: *I always buy tickets for me and mywife - Men har doim o'zim va xotinin uchun chipta sotib olaman; Maria is watching TV right now – Mariya hozir televizor tomosha qilmoqda.* In this case, the medial phase can be expressed by temporary adverbs in combination with the present and progressive temporal form.

The adverbs of the last subgroup serve to designate the final stage that took place long before the moment of speech or was over recently: *He had graduated already - U universitetni allaqachon bitirgan edi.*

Another phase indicator of the English language can be a preposition. There is a certain number of temporary prepositions, which one way or another are related to the distribution of time in space:

- prepositions of the initial phase, which began at the time of speech or will start soon: in, by, at (*Tom will arrive in 3 hours – Tom 3 soatdan keyin keladi*)
- prepositions of the continue phase: in, for, through, during (*He can speak through hours – U bir necha soatgacha gapira oladi*);
- prepositions of the final phase: till/until, since, before (*She waited you till*

the evening - U sizni kechgacha kutdi).

Similar phase characteristics are also possessed by English unions, but their number is not large. The phase unions of a given language can be include the following: when, till, until, by the time, as/while, as soon as, after (*We learned several interesting facts while listening to the lecture – Ma'ruzani tinglash paytida biz bir nechta qiziqarli faktlarni bilib oldik.* First part of the sentence "We learned several interesting facts" describes the phase completion of the action, but the second part of the sentence "while listening to the lecture" denotes the continue, long phase of action.

In English, there are also a number of non-verbal lexical units by which, implicitly or explicitly, one can express phase category.

To begin with, it is worth mentioning a huge layer of nouns, formed either from the verbal units of the language, or served as the basis for the formation of verbs in the future. Examples of this group are serve nouns such as: *start, beginning, continuation, the course, the end, the conclusion* and others. All previously mentioned words have similar verb forms that have a phase meaning, therefore, we have the right to assert that this group of words can also refer to the phase units of the language. One of the features of this kind verbal words is that when translating them you can display in both noun and verb form: *The beginning of studies is always difficult - O'qishning boshlanishi har doim qiyin bo'ladi.*

The next group of nouns implicitly displays a specific phase of the process flow by means of semantics. For example, the word *birth* refers to the process of the birth of a new an individual who is at the beginning of his life path, has not yet having a certain level of life experience for development in society of similar individuals. Therefore, we can assign given lexical unit, the phase of initiation. If we talk further regarding a given word, then the continue phase can be the word *development*, which, on a grand scale, combines the whole

process development, accumulation of life experience, the formation of an individual in his habitat. The final element in this chain is the word *death*. It denotes the final stage of the existence of an organism and its cessation is the final phase. In the life of every human or animal individual, there is a mass of events that have a beginning, a continuation and end. Accordingly, we can talk about the transfer in your or another least given phenomena of the category of phase.

The next lexical means of conveying phase in English language are temporary adverbs expressing temporal relations in a sentence. This group of units, along with verbs and nouns are used to describe a phenomenon or process in time axis, so we can attribute the temporal adverbs of the English language to three main types of phase values:

- beginning of action: *once, before, just, then, earlier, initially, just now, suddenly, introductory*;
- continuation-action: *now, after, later, right after, meanwhile, right now*;
- end of action: *in the future, soon, finally, hind sight* [2,112].

Adverbs of the first subgroup serve to designate the primary stage phenomena that originate in the past, and often it is impossible to identify the starting point of the described phenomenon.

It is understood that the phenomenon took place in the past, continued indefinite time and is finished by the time of speech: *Once he was in Egypt - Bir kuni u Misrda edi.*

Adverbs of the continue phase characterize the procedural of the described phenomenon, accompany the corresponding verbal units and thus create a specific context: *He's singing his favorite song right now - U hozir sevimli qo'shig'ini kuylamoqda.*

Adverbs of the final phase determine the approach of a process or phenomenon to its logical conclusion and its end. In some cases the sentence may have a negative connotation due to the long-term waiting for action to be taken:

In the end, Marina did her homework - Oxirida Marina uy vazifasini qildi..

Another productive way to determine the phase of action in English are conjunctions and prepositions, because each service a word in a given language has its own meaning, its own connotation.

The unions of the initial phase of action include *immediately, hardly that, since(the), as soon as*: *As soon as I understand the topic, I will immediately prepare a report - Mavzuni tushunishim bilan darhol hisobot tayyorlayman.*

Unions *so long, meanwhile, while* actualize the continue phase. They are serve to indicate the duration of the process, its time interval: *While he was playing with the children, she worked - U bolalar bilan o'ynab yurgan vaqtida, u ishlagan.*

The conjunctions *until, after* are used to denote the final phase of an action, that set a time limit and with context determine the conditions for performing an action: *You must pass the exam by Monday - Siz imtihonni dushanbagacha topshirishingiz kerak [2,79].*

Like conjunctions, English prepositions can also convey phase values within a certain context and distributed into groups:

- 1) prepositions denoting the beginning of the action: *from, since, before*, etc;
- 2) prepositions to denote the continue phase: *by, at, in, during*, etc;
- 3) prepositions of the final phase: *after, before, up to/up to+to*, etc [2,89].

Thus, after analyzing a number of foreign sources, it was found that English and English are characterized by a wide the use of contextual means of expressing phase, among which may contain adverbial constructions, verbal nouns, conjunctions and prepositions.

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